

TRADITIONAL NON-LEAFY VEGETABLES OF THE BODO COMMUNITY OF ASSAM: NUTRITIONAL, THERAPEUTIC AND AYURVEDA PERSPECTIVES

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ABSTRACT

Traditional non-leafy vegetables is an inseparable component of the dietary and healthcare practices of Bodo community of Assam. These indigenous food resources possess a significant nutritional and therapeutic potential, however their scientific and Ayurvedic documentation remains limited. This review aims to evaluate the nutritional composition, therapeutic properties and Ayurvedic perspectives. A comprehensive review of published literature was conducted using ethnobotanical surveys, scientific databases and classical Ayurvedic texts. Information regarding nutritional constituents, active phytochemicals, traditional uses, pharmacological activities and ayurvedic attributes was collected and critically analyses. The reviewed vegetables were found to be rich source of carbohydrates, dietary fibre, vitamins, minerals and bioactive compounds with antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antidiabetic,

antimicrobial and hepatoprotective properties. Ayurvedic interpretation revealed that many of these vegetables possess qualities for maintaining doshic balance and promoting overall health. The findings highlight the importance of Bodo traditional vegetables as functional foods with considerable nutritional and therapeutic value. Integration of indigenous knowledge with Ayurvedic principles and modern nutritional science may contribute to dietary diversification, preventive healthcare and preservation of traditional food resources.

Further phytochemical and clinical studies are needed to validate their health promoting potential.

KEYWORDS: Bodo community, indigenous vegetables, ethnobotany, Ayurveda, functional foods.

INTRODUCTION

Food traditions represent an important component of indigenous healthcare systems. The Bodo community is one of the major indigenous groups of Assam, maintains a unique culinary heritage. Their food habit is simple ayurveda food. They are dependent on locally available food items. Traditional Bodo cuisine utilises a wide variety of vegetables from homesteads, agricultural fields, wetlands and nearby forests. These vegetables are incorporated into daily meals and seasonal dishes which are often valued for their medicinal properties.

In recent decades, the global scientific community has increasingly recognised the importance of traditional food systems in promoting national security and preventing chronic diseases. Indigenous vegetable often contains high concentrations of vitamins, minerals, low glycemic index carbohydrates, dietary fibre, antioxidants and other bioactive compounds. Simultaneously, ayurveda has long emphasised the role of vegetables (*Shaka*) in maintaining health and preventing disease.

Although several ethnobotanical surveys have documented Bodo food plants, comprehensive reviews integrating nutritional science, therapeutic evidence, and Ayurvedic interpretation remain scarce. Therefore, the present review aims to evaluate the nutritional composition, clinical significance and ayurvedic relevance of selected non-leafy vegetables traditionally used by the Bodo community of Assam.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A narrative review methodology was adopted. For literature review data was collected from ethnobotanical surveys, peer-reviewed journals, nutritional database and pharmacological studies. Ayurvedic databases was collected from classical ayurvedic texts including *Charaka Samhita*, *Sushruta Samhita*, *Bhavaprakash Nighantu*, *Raja Nighantu* and *Kaiyadeva Nighantu*.

The inclusion criteria were

- Vegetables traditionally consumed by the Bodo community.
- Availability of nutritional information.
- Availability of pharmacological or therapeutic evidence.
- Ayurvedic references or comparable ayurvedic interpretations.

Data were categorised under nutritional value, clinical significance and ayurvedic interpretations.

RESULTS

Table I: Traditional non-leafy vegetables used by the Bodo Community of Assam.

Scientific name	English Name	Bodo Name	Part used	Traditional use
<i>Abelmoschus esculentus</i>	Ladies finger	Bhindi	Green pods, seeds	Often fried, boiled as curry
<i>Agaricus bisporus</i>	Mushroom	Mwikhum	Fruiting body	Food to boost immunity
<i>Alocasia indica (Lour.) Koch.</i>	Arum	Thaso	Young shoot, tuber, tender leaves	Eaten cooked mostly with acidic fruits
<i>Alpinia nigra (Gaertn) Burt.</i>	Sessile joyseed	Tharai	Young shoot and rhizome	Added to curries for the flavour
<i>Amaranthus caudatus</i>	Amaranth	Datha	Leaves and stem	Different types of curry
<i>Amorphophallus paeoniifolius</i>	Elephant foot yam	Wol kochu	Under tuber and occasionally leaves and stems.	Prepared via boiling, backing or frying into curries, pickles etc.
<i>Bambusa balcooa Roxb.</i>	Bamboo	Auwa mewai	Young tender emerging shoot	Cooked with grinded rice and with fish, meat, stored as pickles.
<i>Benincasa hispida</i>	White gourd	Khumbra	Fruit	Immature fruits are fried and mature fruits are cooked.
<i>Colocasia esculenta (Linn.) Schott</i>	Coco yam	Gwswm Thaso	Petiole, root, young leaves and flowers	Eaten as vegetable and curry. Stem is used in preparation of Napham
<i>Cucumis sativas</i>	Cucumber	Thaisum	Fresh fruits	Consumed as raw salad, curry and pickles.
<i>Cucurbita maxima</i>	Pumpkin	Jwgwnath	Fruit, tender leaves and flowers.	Tender leaves and stem as vegetable, flowers fried, fruit cooked with fish.
<i>Discorea alata L</i>	Purple yam	Tha	Subterranean tuber and aerial tuber	Tubers are peeled, sliced and prepared by boiling.
<i>Ipomoea batatas</i>	Sweet potato	Thakum tha	Tuberous root	Roots are boiled, roasted or baked.
<i>Lablab purpureus</i>	Indian beans	Garsi	Pods	Cooked in fish curries, fried
<i>Lagemaria</i>	Bottle gourd	Jati Lao	Fruit, tender leaves,	Young shoot and leaves eaten

<i>siceraria</i>			flower	as vegetable, fruit as curry
<i>Luffa acutangula</i>	Ridge gourd	Jinkha	Fresh immature fruit	Cooked with indigenous fish
<i>Lufa aegyptica</i>	Sponge gourd	Bhol	Fresh immature fruit	Cooked with fish in summer
<i>Momordica charantia Linn</i>	Bitter gourd	Kerela	Fresh immature fruit	Typically stewed with pork (Oma bedor)
<i>Momordica dioca</i>	Teasle gourd	Khangkhree kola	Green immature fruit	Fried, cooked as curries
<i>Moringa oilefera</i>	Drumsticks	Sajina	Fruit, young leaves	Tender moringa leaves is cooked with kharwi (alkali)
<i>Musa paradisiaca</i>	Banana	Thalir	Fruit, pseudo stem, flower bud, rhizome and leaves.	Fruit, stem used as curry, flower bud used as vegetable, rhizome is used to prepare kharwi (alkali)
<i>Pisum sativum</i>	Garden pea	Motor	Seed, pods and young shoots.	Used in preparation of ondra curry (rice powder curry)
<i>Solanum melongena</i>	Brinjal	Phanthao	Fruit	Eaten as mwiwta (mash) with mustard oil, chilli etc.
<i>Trichosanthes dioca</i>	Pointed gourd	Potol	Immature green fruit	Often fried and served alongside rice

Table II: Nutritional profile (per 100gram)

Vegetable	Macronutrients	Micronutrients	Reference
<i>Abelmoschus esculentus</i>	carbohydrate 7.45g, dietary fibre 3.2g, protein 1.93g	Vitamin C, Vitamin K, Folate, potassium, calcium, phosphorus, magnesium.	[1]
<i>Agacarius bisporus</i>	High protein & amino acid, low calorie and low fat,	Natural source of Vitamin D, B-complex, trace amounts of Selenium, potassium.	[2]
<i>Alocasia indica (Lour.) Koch.</i>	high quantity of dietary starch, fibre and carbohydrates	Rich in calcium, potassium and irons. Contains high level of calcium oxalate.	[4,5]
<i>Alpinia nigra (Gaertn) Burt.</i>	Carbohydrate, crude fibre, protein and fat	Abundant in potassium (upto 34.14 mg/g), calcium, magnesium, phosphorus and iron.	[6]
<i>Amaranthus caudatus</i>	Grain contains 14.12-21 % crude protein.	Magnesium, potassium, Calcium and bioavailable iron.	[7]
<i>Amorphophallus paeoniifolius</i>	Crude protein 4.19-4.50%, starch 17.3-20.1%, total sugar 0.14% (which is exceptionally low)	Potassium 327.8mg, phosphorus 166.9mg, calcium 161.1mg, Iron 3.4mg	[9]
<i>Bambusa balcooa Roxb.</i>	High moisture (~90.78%), carbohydrate (5.28%), Protein (2.96%), very low fat content of 0.28%.	Source of essential elements. Potassium, phosphorus, iron, calcium and water soluble vitamins.	[12]
<i>Benincasa hispida</i>	Carbohydrate (1.10-4.00g), Dietary fibre (0.50-2.90g), protein (0.30-0.70g), fat(0.02-0.30g)	Vitamin C (13.0-17.2mg), Calcium (19.0-30.0mg), iron 11.8mg and Potassium.	[15]
<i>Colocasia</i>	Carbohydrates (~75.5%),	Rich in Vitamin C, B1, B2, B6, A,	[18]

<i>esculenta</i> (Linn.) <i>Schott</i>	Protein (~10.9%)	D, E. Leaves are rich source of fibre, protein, calcium, iron, Vitamin A.	
<i>Cucumis sativas</i>	Water (95-96%), carbohydrate (2.16-4.0g), protein (0.65-1g), Fats (0.1g)	Vitamin C, Potassium and Magnesium.	[20]
<i>Cucurbita maxima</i>	Pulp: low calorie & minimal fats (0.2g); Young leaves & stems: superior concentrations of plant based protein, Flowers: Rich in volatile nectar pigments.	Pulp: high source of provitamin A (beta-carotene), vitamin C, potassium and phosphorus; young leaves & stems: abundant bioactive compounds like chlorophylls, lutein and water soluble vitamins.	[21]
<i>Discorea alata</i> L	Carbohydrate (60.3-74.4%), Protein (4.3-8.7%), dietary fibre (4.1-11%), high valued for GI	High concentrations of Potassium, Calcium, Magnesium and Vitamin C.	[23]
<i>Ipomoea batatas</i>	High concentrations of complex carbohydrates, driven by starch and sugar (maltose, sucrose,	Rich in provitamin A(beta-carotene), vitamin C, Vitamin B6, Potassium, phosphorus and manganese.	[25]
<i>Lablab purpureus</i>	Carbohydrates (~60.74g), Protein (23.90-28.00g), Dietary fibre (25.6g)	High concentrations of Potassium (1235mg), Phosphorus (372g), magnesium (283mg), Calcium and iron.	[27]
<i>Lagemaria siceraria</i>	High water (~96%), carbohydrate 3.39g, fibre 0.5g, protein 0.62g, fat 0.2g	Enriched with Vitamin C, Thiamine, Riboflavin, Niacin and trace amounts of Potassium, sodium, calcium and	[30]
<i>Luffa acutangula</i>	Low glycemic complex carbohydrates and abundant dietary fibre.	Rich source of Riboflavin, Thiamine, Niacin, Vitamin C and carotene along with calcium, phosphorus and iron.	[32]
<i>Lufa aegyptica</i>	High water (~93-95%), low calorie (15-18kcal), carbohydrate 3.5g, dietary fibre 0.6g, protein 1.2g	Rich in Thiamine, Riboflavin, Vitamin C and essential folates, potassium, calcium, phosphorus and magnesium.	[34]
<i>Momordica charantia</i> Linn	93.2% water, protein 18.02%, fats 0.76%, naturally rich in carbohydrates and dietary fibre.	Vitamin C, Vitamin A, Thiamine, Riboflavin and niacin, seed contains healthy fatty acids.	[35]
Vegetable	Macronutrients	Micronutrients	Reference
<i>Momordica dioca</i>	Carbohydrates 45-47.92%, protein 18-19.38% (highest among cucurbits), fibre 21.3-22%, fat 4-4.7%.	Calcium 33-35mg, phosphorus 42-45mg, iron 4-5mg, sodium 1.5mg, potassium 8.25mg, Magnesium, zinc and manganese. Vitamin A, B1, B2, B3, B5, B6, B9, B12, Vitamin D2 and D3, Biotin and Vitamin K.	[36]
<i>Moringa oleifera</i>	Dried leaf powder: Carbohydrate 38.2g, Protein 27.1g, fibre 19.2g, fat 2.3g.	Calcium 1324mg(17x more than milk), Iron 28.2mg(25x more than spinach), potassium 1324mg(15x	[37]

		more than banana), Magnesium 368mg, Vitamin C(17.3mg, in raw 220mg, 7x more than in orange), Vitamin A 18.9mg(4x more than carrot).	
<i>Musa paradisiaca</i>	Carbohydrates 23.0g, fibre 2.6g, protein 1.1g, fat 0.3g,	Potassium, phosphate, magnesium, calcium, iron, Vitamin C, Vitamin B6, Vitamin A, Vitamin B9(folate).	[38]
<i>Pisum sativum</i>	Called poor man's meat due to high protein and minerals, protein 5.4g, carbohydrates 14.5g, fibre	Vitamin K, Vitamin C, phosphorus, iron, manganese and zinc.	[40]
<i>Solanum melongena</i>	Carbohydrates 4.70-5.88g, dietary fibre 2.80-3.40g, protein 0.80-1.01g, fat 0.18-0.20g	Potassium ~230mg, Calcium 7.94-9.0 mg, phosphorus 22.5-25.0mg, Magnesium, iron, vitamin C, Vitamin K, Vitamin B6, folate and niacin.	[42]
<i>Trichosanthes dioica</i>	Good source of carbohydrates	Vitamin A, Vitamin C and trace elements like Magnesium, Potassium, copper, sulphur and chloride.	[44]

Table III: Therapeutic significance

Vegetable	Pharmacological activity	Reference
<i>Abelmoschus esculentus</i>	Antidiabetic, Anticancer, Hypolipidemic, Gastroprotective, antioxidant, Gastroprotective.	[1]
<i>Agacarius bisporus</i>	Immunomodulatory, antioxidant & cellular defence, promotes healthy gut microbiome functions, Hypolipidemic	[3]
<i>Alocasia indica (Lour.) Koch.</i>	Antioxidant, anti-inflammatory and Antimicrobial.	[4,5]
<i>Alpinia nigra (Gaertn) Burt.</i>	Antimicrobial, Antidiabetic, antioxidant, preventative of ageing, reduced inflammation, protecting cardiovascular system.	[6]
<i>Amaranthus caudatus</i>	Seeds: Antidiabetic, antibacterial, Antimicrobial and Antifungal; leaf: Hepatoprotective and helps in biotin deficiency; whole plant: Anthelmintic, Antimalarial and cardiovascular protection.	[8]
<i>Amorphophallus paeoniifolius</i>	Curative action on hemorrhoids through anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties. Metabolic regulation (Antihyperglycemic) due to low glycemic index. Analgesic & anti-inflammatory.	[10,11]
<i>Bambusa balcooa Roxb.</i>	Antidiabetic and Hypoglycaemic potential, Antioxidant and Gastroprotective,	[13,14]
<i>Benincasa hispida</i>	Gastroprotective, Neuropharmacological & anti-stress, Metabolic regulation - Hypoglycaemic and Hypolipidemic, anti-urolithiac, anti-angiogenic (seed extract)	[16,17]

<i>Colocasia esculenta</i> (Linn.) Schott	Antidiabetic, Antimicrobial, Antifungal, antioxidant-inflammatory, Hepatoprotective, Anticancer and nervine tonic.	[19]
<i>Cucumis sativas</i>	Anti-inflammatory & analgesic, antioxidant and free radical scavenging, hypoglycaemic.	[20]
<i>Cucurbita maxima</i>	Antidiabetic: low glycemic load, antioxidant and tissue protection, anti-inflammatory, immunomodulatory, Anthelmintic.	[22]
<i>Discorea alata L</i>	Antidiabetic hypoglycaemic, antioxidant and, anti-inflammatory, cardioprotective and Hypolipidemic.	[24]
<i>Ipomoea batatas</i>	Antidiabetic, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, immunomodulatory and Gastroprotective.	[26]
<i>Lablab purpureus</i>	Antiviral, Bone health and anti-Osteoporotic, hypolipidemic, Antidiabetic.	[28,29]
<i>Lagemaria siceraria</i>	Cardioprotective, Hypolipidemic, diuretic and renal protection, Gastroprotective and Hepatoprotective.	[31]
<i>Luffa acutangula</i>	Hepatoprotective and anti-jaundice, Antidiabetic, antioxidant-inflammatory and analgesic, Gastroprotective and laxative.	[33]
Vegetable	Pharmacological activity	Reference
<i>Lufa aegyptica</i>	Antidiabetic, Hepatoprotective, anti-inflammatory analgesic, immune and anti-allergy support.	[34]
<i>Momordica charantia Linn</i>	Antidiabetic, antioxidant, Anticancer, Antimicrobial, antiviral, anti-inflammatory, immunomodulatory.	[35]
<i>Momordica dioca</i>	Antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, Antidiabetic, reducing bad cholesterol, nephroprotective, Anticancer, Antimicrobial and analgesic.	[36]
<i>Moringa oilefera</i>	Antioxidant, Anticancer, Hepatoprotective, cardioprotective, anti-ulcer/gastroprotective, analgesic, immunomodulatory, anti-obesity, anti-allergic, Antidiabetic and diuretic.	[37]
<i>Musa paradisiaca</i>	Antidiabetic, antioxidant, Antidiarrheal, antidepressants, Antiulcer, Antimicrobial, Hypolipidemic, Antihypertensive, Hepatoprotective.	[39]
<i>Pisum sativum</i>	Antidiabetic, promotes Cardiovascular health, antioxidant and anti-inflammatory.	[41]
<i>Solanum melongena</i>	Antioxidant, cardioprotective, Anticancer and glycemic control.	[43]
<i>Trichosanthes dioca</i>	Antidiabetic, antioxidant, Hepatoprotective, Hypolipidemic, anti-inflammatory, Antifungal and antibacterial.	[45]

Table IV. Ayurvedic attributes

Vegetable	Sanskrit name	Rasa	Guna	Virya	Doshakarma	Reference
<i>Abelmoschus esculentus</i>	Bhindika	Madhura (sweet), tikta (bitter).	Guru (heavy), snigdha (unctuous)	Shita (cold)	Kaphakara, Vata-Pitta hara, Rakta shodak, Sotha hara.	[46]
<i>Agacarius</i>	Chhatraka	Madhura	Laghu(light),	Shita (cold)	reduces Vata, Pitta,	[47]

<i>bisporus</i>		(sweet)	Snigdha(unctuous), picchila (slimy)		increases Kapha, Nutritious and aphrodisiac, brimhana.	
<i>Alocasia indica</i> (Lour.) Koch.	Manakanda	Madhura (sweet)	Guru (heavy), snigdha (unctuous)	Shita (cold)	reduces Vata, Pitta, easily digestible, mutrajanana, mild laxative.	[48]
<i>Alpinia nigra</i> (Gaertn) Burtt.	Mahavari vacha	Katu (pungent),	Laghu (light), Tikshna (penetrating), ruksha (dry)	Ushna (hot)	Reduces Kapha-Vata, Appetizer, improves voice, kantha vishuddhikara.	[49]
<i>Amaranthus</i> <i>caudatus</i>	Tanduliyaka	Madhura (sweet)	Laghu (light), ruksha (dry)	Shita (cold)	Pacifies Pitta-Kapha, mild laxative, whole plant is Mutrala (diuretic), beneficial in mutrakriccha.	[50]
<i>Amorphophallus</i> <i>paeoniifolius</i>	Suranakanda	Katu (pungent), Kashaya (Astringent)	Laghu (light), Ruksha (dry), Tikshna (penetrating)	Ushna (hot)	Pacifies Kapha-Vata, deepana, pachana and Appetizer, benefits in Arsha,	[51]
<i>Bambusa</i> <i>balcooa</i> Roxb.	Kareera	Katu (pungent)	Ruksha (dry), guru (heavy), sara (mobile)	Ushna (hot)	Balances Kapha, increases Vata-Pitta, it relieves burning and painful micturation.	[52]
<i>Benincasa</i> <i>hispidia</i>	Kushmanda	Madhura (sweet)	Laghu (light), snigdha (slimy)	Shita (cold)	Pacifies Vata-pitta, Medhya, Mutrajanan, Balya, useful in Raktapitta, unmada, apasmara, prameha.	[53]
<i>Colocasia</i> <i>esculenta</i> (Linn.) Schott	Aaloki	Madhura (sweet)	Guru (heavy), snigdha (slimy)	Shita (cold)	Increases kapha, balakrith (promotes strength), Vistambha (causes constipation), useful in hepatomegaly.	[54]
<i>Cucumis sativas</i>	Trapusha	Madhura (sweet)	Laghu (light), ruksha (dry)	Shita (cold)	Pittahara (reduces pitta), Mutrala, Shothahara, seed is useful in Bastishula.	[55]
<i>Cucurbita</i> <i>maxima</i>	Kushmandi	Madhura (sweet)	Ruksha (dry), guru (heavy)	Shita (cold)	Raw: Increases Vata, pitta, Kapha; Ripe: Balances Kapha-Vata,	[56]
<i>Discorea alata</i> L	Varahikand a	Madhura (sweet), Katu (pungent)	Laghu (light), Snigdha (slimy)	Ushna (hot)	Balances Kapha- Vata, increases Pitta, strength promoting, aphrodisiac	[57]
<i>Ipomoea</i> <i>batatas</i>	Pindalu, Shakarkand	Madhura (sweet)	Guru (heavy), snigdha (slimy)	Shita (cold)	Pacifies Vata, Pitta, increases kapha, Vrushya, Balya	[58]
Vegetable	Sanskrit name	Rasa	Guna	Virya	Doshakarma	Reference
<i>Lablab</i> <i>purpureus</i>	Nishpaava - simbi	Madhura (sweet), kashaya (astringent)	Ruksha(dry), guru(heavy), vidahi (causes burning)	Ushna (hot)	Increases Vata-Pitta, increases breast-milk, pitta, blood	[59]

<i>Lagemaria siceraria</i>	Alabu, Mahaphala	Tikta (pungent)	Laghu(light), Ruksha (dry)	Shita(cold)	Balances Vata-Pitta, Vamaka, Ahrudya. Bitter variety is used for therapeutic purpose.	[60]
<i>Luffa acutangula</i>	Koshataki	Tikta (bitter)	Laghu (light), ruksha(dry)	Ushna (hot)	Kapha-pitta hara, Vamaka(seed), Deepana, leaves paste is useful in various skin diseases.	[61]
<i>Lufa aegyptica</i>	Dhamargava	Tikta (bitter),	Laghu (light), ruksha (dry)	Ushna (hot)	Kapha-pitta hara, Vamaka, Deepana.	[62]
<i>Momordica charantia Linn</i>	Karvellaka	Tikta (bitter), katu (pungent)	Laghu (light), ruksha (dry)	Sheeta (cold), Ahima (neither cold nor hot)	Kapha-pitta hara, Deepana, Krimighna, mutrajanana, useful in Prameha, fruit as curry and leaves paste in useful in skin disorders.	[63]
<i>Momordica dioca</i>	Kakoda, Vandya karkoti	Tikta (bitter)	Laghu(light),	Ushna (hot)	Balances Vata, increases pitta, helps in Prameha, root paste act as Rakta stambhana.	[64]
<i>Moringa oilefera</i>	Shigru	Katu (pungent), tikta (bitter)	Laghu, Tikshna, Ruksha	Ushna (hot)	Pacifies Kapha-Vata. Tender leaves consumption act as laxative, fruit is Antimicrobial.	[65]
<i>Musa paradisiaca</i>	Kadali	Ripe: Madhura; Raw: Kashaya	Ripe: guru, hima, Raw: Laghu, ruksha	Shita (cold)	Ripe: aphrodisiac, nourishing, increases sperm production. Raw: Prameha, Diarrhoea.	[66]
<i>Pisum sativum</i>	Kalaya	Madhura (sweet), kashaya (astringent)	Laghu (light), Ruksha (dry)		Increases Vata, pacifies Pitta-kapha	[67]
<i>Solanum melongena</i>	Vartaku	Madhura (sweet)	Laghu(light)	Ushna (hot)	Balances Kapha-Vata,	[68]
<i>Trichosanthes dioca</i>	Patola	Tikta (bitter), katu (pungent)	Laghu (light), Ruksha (dry)	Ushna (hot)	Balances Kapha-Pitta	[69]

DISCUSSION

The present review demonstrates that non-leafy vegetables which are traditionally consumed by the Bodo community are valuable source of nutrients and bioactive compounds. Root and tuber vegetable such as taro, sweet potato and purple yam provide energy, dietary fibre and essential minerals. Fruit vegetables including pumpkin, bottle gourd, cucumber, ridge gourd and bitter gourd are rich in antioxidants and vitamins while maintaining low caloric density.

Several vegetables exhibited scientifically validated antidiabetic properties. Bitter gourd, pumpkin, sweet potato, teasle gourd and taro have demonstrated glucose-lowering effects in

experimental studies. This observation is particularly important considering the increasing burden of metabolic disorders in modern society.

Ayurvedic analysis revealed that many vegetables possess Tikta (bitter) and Madhura (sweet) rasa, which are traditionally associated with metabolic regulation, nourishment and dosha balance. Bitter vegetables such as Karvellaka, Koshataki and Dhamargava are Kapha-Pitta hara and have traditionally been indicated in Prameha, Kustha and digestive disorders. Similarly, nourishing vegetables such as Kushmanda, Varahi kanda and kadali serve as Balya and Brimhana foods.

The convergence of indigenous knowledge, scientific evidence and Ayurvedic principles highlights the importance of these vegetables as functional foods. Preservation of traditional food practices may contribute to national food security, biodiversity conservation and preventive healthcare.

CONCLUSION

Traditional non-leafy vegetable of the Bodo community constitute an important component of indigenous food system and possess a significant nutritional, therapeutic and ayurvedic value. These vegetables provide essential nutrients, antioxidants compounds and potential disease-preventive effects. Scientific findings largely support traditional claims regarding their health benefits. Integration of ethnobotanical knowledge with modern nutritional science and Ayurveda can facilitate the development of evidence-based dietary recommendations and promote the conservation of indigenous food resources. Future clinical and phytochemical studies are warranted to further validate their therapeutic potential.

REFERENCES

1. Elkhalfa AEO, Alshammari E, Adnan M, Alcantara JC, Awadelkareem AM, Eltoum NE, Mehmood K, Panda BP, Ashraf SA. Okra (*Abelmoschus Esculentus*) as a Potential Dietary Medicine with Nutraceutical Importance for Sustainable Health Applications. *Molecules*, 2021 Jan 28; 26(3): 696. doi: 10.3390/molecules26030696. PMID: 33525745; PMCID: PMC7865958.
2. Rautela, Indra & Arora, Himani & Binjola, Atul & Dheer, Pallavi. (2019). Potential and Nutrition Value of Mushroom and Its Cultivation; an Insight Review, 9: 22574- 22582.
3. Raman Krishnamoorthi, Moovendran Srinivash, Pambayan Ulagan Mahalingam, Balasubramanian Malaikozhundan, Dietary nutrients in edible mushroom, *Agaricus*

- bisporus and their radical scavenging, antibacterial, and antifungal effects, *Process Biochemistry*, 2022; 121: 0-17, ISSN 1359-5113, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procbio.2022.06.021>.
4. Gupta, Kritika & Kumar, Ashwani & Tomer, Vidisha & Kumar, Vikas & Saini, Mona. (2019). Potential of Colocasia leaves in human nutrition: Review on nutritional and phytochemical properties. *Journal of Food Biochemistry*, 43: e12878. [10.1111/jfbc.12878](https://doi.org/10.1111/jfbc.12878).
 5. Neog, Bijoy & Bora, Devanjal & Mehmud, Selim & Das, Kangkan & Bharali, Bk & Das, Dimbeshwar & Hatimuria, Romesh & Raidongia, Luhit. (2016). Credibility of medico-ethnobotanical uses of members of Aroid family in Assam (India), 4: 9-14.
 6. Daimary M, Islary P, Daimari R. Phytochemical, proximate analysis and antioxidant activity of the rhizome of *Alpinia nigra* (Gaertn.)B.L. Burt (Zingiberaceae) in Tamulpur district, Assam. *Plant Science Today*, 2024; 11(3): 172-182. <https://doi.org/10.14719/pst.2929>
 7. Joshi N, Verma KC. A review on nutrition value of Amaranth (*Amaranthus caudatus* L.): The crop of future. *J Pharmacogn Phytochem.*, 2020; 9(4): 317–319.
 8. Jimoh, Muhali & Afolayan, A.J. & Lewu, Francis. (2019). Therapeutic uses of *amaranthus caudatus* L.. *Tropical Biomedicine*, 36. 1038-1053.
 9. Dey YN, Wanjari MM, Kumar D, Lomash V, Jadhav AD. Curative effect of *Amorphophallus paeoniifolius* tuber on experimental hemorrhoids in rats. *J Ethnopharmacol.*, 2016 Nov 4; 192: 183-191. doi: 10.1016/j.jep.2016.07.042. Epub 2016 Jul 16. PMID: 27426509
 10. Arva, Harshavardhan & Bhaskar, Jamuna & Salimath, Veeresh & M, Aradhya. (2012). Anti-diabetic Effect of Elephant-foot Yam (*Amorphophallus paeoniifoliosus* (Dennst.) Nicolson) in Streptozotocin-induced Diabetic Rats. *International Journal of Biomedical and Pharmaceutical research*.
 11. A., H., & A. T., S. V. (2019). Analgesic activity of aqueous extract of *Amorphophallus paeoniifolius* in Swiss albino mice. *International Journal of Basic & Clinical Pharmacology*, 8(6): 1327–1330.
 12. Acharya B, Behera A, Sahu PK, Mishra DP, Purohit S, Chowdhury B, et al. Exploring the mineral content, nutritional, and phytochemical composition of aqueous shoot extracts of bamboo for ethnopharmacological significance from the Niyamgiri hill range, Kalahandi, Odisha, India. *Advances in Bamboo Science*, 2024; 9: 100110. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bamboo.2024.100110>

13. Goyal AK, Middha SK, Usha T, Sen A. Analysis of toxic, antidiabetic and antioxidant potential of *Bambusa balcooa* Roxb. leaf extracts in alloxan-induced diabetic rats. *3 Biotech*, 2017 Jun; 7(2): 120. doi: 10.1007/s13205-017-0776-8. Epub 2017 May 31. PMID: 28567632; PMCID: PMC5451367.
14. Long F, Hu Z, Luo H, Chu Z, Li S, Zhou Y, Li A, Luo F. Remodeling of Bamboo (*Phyllostachys edulis*) Shoot Polysaccharides by *Monascus purpureus* Fermentation Enhances Antioxidant Protection in Caco-2 Cells. *Foods*, 2026 Feb 14; 15(4): 704. doi: 10.3390/foods15040704. PMID: 41750896; PMCID: PMC12939474.
15. Shwetha P.*, Lovelin Jerald, Comprehensive Review of *Benincasa hispida* (White Pumpkin): Nutritional Profile, Bioactive Compounds, and Functional Applications in Food and Health Industries, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2025; 3(3): 1915-1923. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15055820>
16. Anjali M. Wankhade, Manish M. Wanjari, Rupali Dhuldhar, Umair Akhtar. Pharmacological Evaluation of *Benincasa Hispida* Cogn. Fruit on Chronic Foot Shock Induced Stress in Mice. *Research Journal of Pharmacology and Pharmacodynamics*, 2023; 15(2): 49-4. doi: 10.52711/2321-5836.2023.00010
17. Neeralakeri SS, Deshmukh S, Varma A, Varma RG. A Comprehensive Literature Review On *Kushmanda*(*Benincasa Hispida* *Thunip*) As *Medhya* (IQ Booster). *J Pharm Bioallied Sci.*, 2025 Sep; 17(Suppl 3): S2115-S2118. doi: 10.4103/jpbs.jpbs_629_25. Epub 2025 Sep 8. PMID: 41164654; PMCID: PMC12563348.
18. Aditika, Kapoor B, Singh S, Kumar P. Taro (*Colocasia esculenta*): Zero wastage orphan food crop for food and nutritional security. *South African Journal of Botany*, 2022; 145: 157-169.
19. Swapnil S. Lad, Swati U. Kolhe, Omkar A. Devade, Chetashri N. Patil, Rohit D. Nalawade, Manthan R. Rode. A Review on Medicinal properties of *Colocasia esculenta* Linn. *Research Journal of Pharmacology and Pharmacodynamics*, 2023; 15(3): 144-8. doi: 10.52711/2321-5836.2023.00026
20. Amani T, Surenthar M, Shanmugam R. Anti-inflammatory and Antioxidant Activity of *Cucumis sativus* and *Citrus macroptera* Herbal Formulation: An In-Vitro Study. *Cureus*, 2024 Jan 7; 16(1): e51818. doi: 10.7759/cureus.51818. PMID: 38327926; PMCID: PMC10847068.
21. Jahan F, Islam MB, Moulick SP, Al Bashera M, Hasan MS, Tasnim N, Saha T, Boby F, Waliullah M, Saha AK, Hossain A, Ferdousi L, Rahman MM, Saha BK, Huda Bhuiyan MN. Nutritional characterization and antioxidant properties of various edible portions of

- Cucurbita maxima*: A potential source of nutraceuticals. *Heliyon*, 2023 May 29; 9(6): e16628. doi: 10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e16628. PMID: 37303524; PMCID: PMC10248113.
22. Yadav M, Jain S, Tomar R, Prasad GB, Yadav H. Medicinal and biological potential of pumpkin: an updated review. *Nutr Res Rev.*, 2010 Dec; 23(2): 184-90. doi: 10.1017/S0954422410000107. PMID: 21110905.
23. Obidiegwu JE, Lyons JB, Chilaka CA. The *Dioscorea* Genus (Yam)-An Appraisal of Nutritional and Therapeutic Potentials. *Foods*, 2020 Sep 16; 9(9): 1304. doi: 10.3390/foods9091304. PMID: 32947880; PMCID: PMC7555206.
24. Salehi B, Sener B, Kilic M, Sharifi-Rad J, Naz R, Yousaf Z, Mudau FN, Fokou PVT, Ezzat SM, El Bishbishy MH, Taheri Y, Lucariello G, Durazzo A, Lucarini M, Suleria HAR, Santini A. *Dioscorea* Plants: A Genus Rich in Vital Nutra-pharmaceuticals-A Review. *Iran J Pharm Res.*, 2019 Fall; 18(Suppl1): 68-89. doi: 10.22037/ijpr.2019.112501.13795. PMID: 32802090; PMCID: PMC7393038.
25. Murugan, Revathi & M, Nithya & S, Vignesh. (2022). Literature Review on *Ipomoea batatas* (L.) Lam. *International Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Research*, 26: 33-44.
26. Boukhers I, Morel S, Kongolo J, Domingo R, Servent A, Ollier L, Kodja H, Petit T, Poucheret P. Immunomodulatory and Antioxidant Properties of *Ipomoea batatas* Flour and Extracts Obtained by Green Extraction. *Curr Issues Mol Biol.*, 2023 Aug 22; 45(9): 6967-6985. doi: 10.3390/cimb45090440. PMID: 37754224; PMCID: PMC10529725.
27. Pandey, Dileep & Adhiguru, P. & Pandey, Anjula & Singh, Praveen. (2021). An Underexplored Diversity in “Yoksik Peron” [*Lablab purpureus* (L.) Sweet] in East Siang, Arunachal Pradesh, India. 10.21203/rs.3.rs-713936/ v1.
28. Bhat SS, Pradeep S, Patil SS, Flores-Holguín N, Glossman-Mitnik D, Frau J, Sommano SR, Ali N, Mohany M, Shivamallu C, Prasad SK, Kollur SP. Preliminary Evaluation of *Lablab purpureus* Phytochemicals for Anti-BoHV-1 Activity Using In Vitro and In Silico Approaches. *ACS Omega*, 2023 Jun 14; 8(25): 22684-22697. doi: 10.1021/acsomega.3c01478. PMID: 37396248; PMCID: PMC10308559.
29. Chetia, Snigdha & Kumari, Tapasya & C., Nickhil & Deka, Sankar. (2025). A comprehensive review on the nutritional, medicinal, and functional potential of *Dolichos lablab*. *Discover Food*. 5. 10.1007/s44187-025-00500-9.
30. Saeed M, Khan MS, Amir K, Bi JB, Asif M, Madni A, Kamboh AA, Manzoor Z, Younas U and Chao S (2022) *Lagenaria siceraria* fruit: A review of its phytochemistry, pharmacology, and promising traditional uses. *Front. Nutr*, 9: 927361. doi:

- 10.3389/fnut.2022.927361
31. Chandak, Chanchal & Ambhore, Jaya & Gaikwad, Kiran & Adhao, Vaibhav S.. (2024). MEDICINAL SIGNIFICANCE OF LAGENARIA SICERARIA; A SUMMARIZING ASSESSMENT. *International Journal of Pharmacognosy*, 11: 235-246. 10.13040/IJPSR.0975-8232.IJP.11(6).235-46.
32. Belemkar, S., Sharma, M., Ghode, P., Shendge, P.N. (2021). Bioactive Compounds of Ridge Gourd (*Luffa acutangula* (L.) Roxb.). In: Murthy, H.N., Paek, K.Y. (eds) *Bioactive Compounds in Underutilized Vegetables and Legumes*. Reference Series in Phytochemistry. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-44578-2_22-1
33. Ahirwar S, Kurmi D, Kurmi D, Nisha P. *Luffa acutangula*: A brief review on phytochemical and pharmacological profile. *Asian J Pharm Pharmacol*. 2023; 9(1): 20-28. doi: <https://doi.org/10.31024/ajpp.2023.9.1.4>
34. Swamy KRM. Origin, distribution, taxonomy, botanical description, genetic diversity and breeding of *Luffa* spp. *Int J Curr Res.*, 2023 Mar; 15(03): 24105-24122. doi: <https://doi.org/10.24941/ijcr.44777.03.202>
35. Sharma SK, Baliyan P, Alam A. *Momordica charantia* L.: Unlocking its Potential as a Nutritional Food Through Ethnomedicinal and Pharmacological Properties. *Res J Bot.*, 2024; 19(1): 31-40. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.3923/rjb.2024.31.40>
36. Chatterjee S, Sagar P, Tiwari AK, Upadhyay D, Tiwari S, Singh A, Tiwari B, Sharma A, Mishra YK, Khan R, Singh A, Tiwari JK and Kumar A (2026) Spine gourd (*Momordica dioica* Roxb.): an orphan climbing vine attaining new heights due to its healthcare properties. *Front. Pharmacol.*, 17: 1761413. doi: 10.3389/fphar.2026.1761413
37. Pareek A, Pant M, Gupta MM, Kashania P, Ratan Y, Jain V, Pareek A, Chuturgoon AA. *Moringa oleifera*: An Updated Comprehensive Review of Its Pharmacological Activities, Ethnomedicinal, Phytopharmaceutical Formulation, Clinical, Phytochemical, and Toxicological Aspects. *Int J Mol Sci.*, 2023 Jan 20; 24(3): 2098. doi: 10.3390/ijms24032098. PMID: 36768420; PMCID: PMC9916933.
38. Oyeyinka BO, Afolayan AJ. Comparative Evaluation of the Nutritive, Mineral, and Antinutritive Composition of *Musa sinensis* L. (Banana) and *Musa paradisiaca* L. (Plantain) Fruit Compartments. *Plants (Basel)*, 2019 Dec 12; 8(12): 598. doi: 10.3390/plants8120598. PMID: 31842474; PMCID: PMC6963461.
39. Kore P, Pore G, Shinde S, Tambe P, Bandawane D. A review on phytochemicals and pharmacological activities for *Musa paradisiaca* Linn. *IJBPAS*, 2023 Dec; 12(12): 5630-5639. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.31032/IJBPAS/2023/12.12.7627>

40. Zilani MN, Sultana T, Asabur Rahman SM, Anisuzzman M, Islam MA, Shilpi JA, Hossain MG. Chemical composition and pharmacological activities of *Pisum sativum*. *BMC Complement Altern Med.*, 2017 Mar 27; 17(1): 171. doi: 10.1186/s12906-017-1699-y. PMID: 28347309; PMCID: PMC5368943.
41. Savage, Geoffrey & S, Deo. (1989). The Nutritional Value of Peas (*Pisum sativum*). A Literature Review. *Nutr Abstr Rev.* 59.
42. Lahon, Gaurav & Buragohain, Nayanmoni & Goswami, Ratna & Bora, Budha & Gogoi, Kishalayee & Chetia, Dipandita & Konwar, Biswajit & Mishra, Ranima. (2026). Evaluation of Some Brinjal (*Solanum melongena* L.) Cultivars of Karbi Anglong District, Assam for Growth, Yield and Profitability. *International Journal of Economic Plants.* 13. 01-06. 10.23910/2/2026.6869b.
43. Sonmez, Kenan & Kafkas, Ebru & Kaplan, Gulcur & Boyacı, Hafize & Ellialtioglu, Sebnem. (2020). THE EGGPLANT (*Solanum melongena* L.) AS A FRUIT VEGETABLE AND MEDICINAL PLANT.
44. Malek, M., Miah, M. B., AL-Amin, M., Khanam, D., & Khatun, M. (2008), "In vitro regeneration in pointed gourd", *Bangladesh Journal of Agricultural Research*, 32(3): 461–471, doi: 10.3329/bjar.v32i3.548
45. Kumar N, Singh S, Manvi, Gupta R. *Trichosanthes dioica* Roxb.: An overview. *Pharmacogn Rev.*, 2012 Jan; 6(11): 61-7. doi: 10.4103/0973-7847.95886. PMID: 22654406; PMCID: PMC3358970.
46. Agnivesha. *Caraka Samhita: Part-I (Sutrasthana)*. With 'Ayurveda-Dipika' Sanskrit Commentary by Sri Cakrapanidatta and 'Tattvaparakasini' Hindi Commentary. Dwivedi L, editor, commentator; Dwivedi BK, Goswami PK, co-editors, commentators. Varanasi: Chowkhamba Krishnadas Academy, [2024]; 534.
47. Chunekar KC, commentator; Pandey GS, editor. *Bhavaprakasa Nighantu (Indian Materia Medica)* of Sri Bhavamisra. Reprint ed. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Bharati Academy, 2002; 703.
48. Chunekar KC, commentator; Pandey GS, editor. *Bhavaprakasa Nighantu (Indian Materia Medica)* of Sri Bhavamisra. Reprint ed. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Bharati Academy, 2002; 699.
49. Chunekar KC, commentator; Pandey GS, editor. *Bhavaprakasa Nighantu (Indian Materia Medica)* of Sri Bhavamisra. Reprint ed. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Bharati Academy, 2002; 44-46.
50. Chunekar KC, commentator; Pandey GS, editor. *Bhavaprakasa Nighantu (Indian*

- Materia Medica) of Sri Bhavamisra. Reprint ed. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Bharati Academy, 2002; 667.
51. Chunekar KC, commentator; Pandey GS, editor. Bhavaprakasa Nighantu (Indian Materia Medica) of Sri Bhavamisra. Reprint ed. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Bharati Academy, 2002; 693.
52. Sushruta. Susruta-Samhita: Vol. I (Sutrasthana). With English translation of text and Dalhaṇa's commentary alongwith critical notes. Sharma PV, editor, translator. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Visvabharati, 2013; 215.
53. Chunekar KC, commentator; Pandey GS, editor. Bhavaprakasa Nighantu (Indian Materia Medica) of Sri Bhavamisra. Reprint ed. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Bharati Academy, 2002; 681.
54. Chunekar KC, commentator; Pandey GS, editor. Bhavaprakasa Nighantu (Indian Materia Medica) of Sri Bhavamisra. Reprint ed. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Bharati Academy, 2002; 696.
55. Chunekar KC, commentator; Pandey GS, editor. Bhavaprakasa Nighantu (Indian Materia Medica) of Sri Bhavamisra. Reprint ed. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Bharati Academy, 2002; 562.
56. Chunekar KC, commentator; Pandey GS, editor. Bhavaprakasa Nighantu (Indian Materia Medica) of Sri Bhavamisra. Reprint ed. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Bharati Academy, 2002; 680.
57. Chunekar KC, commentator; Pandey GS, editor. Bhavaprakasa Nighantu (Indian Materia Medica) of Sri Bhavamisra. Reprint ed. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Bharati Academy, 2002; 694.
58. Chunekar KC, commentator; Pandey GS, editor. Bhavaprakasa Nighantu (Indian Materia Medica) of Sri Bhavamisra. Reprint ed. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Bharati Academy, 2002; 695.
59. Chunekar KC, commentator; Pandey GS, editor. Bhavaprakasa Nighantu (Indian Materia Medica) of Sri Bhavamisra. Reprint ed. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Bharati Academy, 2002; 646.
60. Chunekar KC, commentator; Pandey GS, editor. Bhavaprakasa Nighantu (Indian Materia Medica) of Sri Bhavamisra. Reprint ed. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Bharati Academy, 2002; 681-682.
61. Chunekar KC, commentator; Pandey GS, editor. Bhavaprakasa Nighantu (Indian Materia Medica) of Sri Bhavamisra. Reprint ed. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Bharati

- Academy, 2002; 685.
62. Chunekar KC, commentator; Pandey GS, editor. Bhavaprakasa Nighantu (Indian Materia Medica) of Sri Bhavamisra. Reprint ed. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Bharati Academy, 2002; 685.
63. Chunekar KC, commentator; Pandey GS, editor. Bhavaprakasa Nighantu (Indian Materia Medica) of Sri Bhavamisra. Reprint ed. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Bharati Academy, 2002; 683.
64. Chunekar KC, commentator; Pandey GS, editor. Bhavaprakasa Nighantu (Indian Materia Medica) of Sri Bhavamisra. Reprint ed. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Bharati Academy, 2002; 691.
65. Chunekar KC, commentator; Pandey GS, editor. Bhavaprakasa Nighantu (Indian Materia Medica) of Sri Bhavamisra. Reprint ed. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Bharati Academy, 2002; 340.
66. Chunekar KC, commentator; Pandey GS, editor. Bhavaprakasa Nighantu (Indian Materia Medica) of Sri Bhavamisra. Reprint ed. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Bharati Academy, 2002; 557.
67. Chunekar KC, commentator; Pandey GS, editor. Bhavaprakasa Nighantu (Indian Materia Medica) of Sri Bhavamisra. Reprint ed. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Bharati Academy, 2002; 648.
68. Chunekar KC, commentator; Pandey GS, editor. Bhavaprakasa Nighantu (Indian Materia Medica) of Sri Bhavamisra. Reprint ed. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Bharati Academy, 2002; 690.
69. Chunekar KC, commentator; Pandey GS, editor. Bhavaprakasa Nighantu (Indian Materia Medica) of Sri Bhavamisra. Reprint ed. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Bharati Academy, 2002; 686.